

SDN-enabled Flexible Quantum Channel Allocation for CV-QKD Coexistence with Programmable Sliceable Transceivers

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Abstract *The developed open-source TeraFlowSDN controller is integrated with a real CV-QKD system tailored to support quantum channel remote configuration, which is experimentally demonstrated for dynamic allocation and facilitating coexistence in scenarios with programmable sliceable transceivers, towards QKD integration into optical networks for quantum secure connectivity. ©2025 The Author(s)*

Introduction

Future optical networks should provide ultra-high capacity connectivity, ensuring sustainability and security in view of supporting 6G and AI services.

On the one hand, advanced high-capacity transceivers exploiting multiple bands and spatial division multiplexing (SDM) enable scalability and multi-Tb/s capacities. Programmable and modular sliceable bandwidth/bitrate variable transceivers (S-BVT) provide scalability in a grow-as-needed fashion and dynamic traffic adaptation, enabling flexible rate, and adaptive reach/connectivity to multiple endpoints [1-3].

On the other hand, quantum key distribution (QKD) enables long-term security and quantum secure communications. Continuous variable QKD (CV-QKD), thanks to its compatibility with classical systems, offers potential cost saving and broad-scale deployment also in view of using photonic integration [4-7]. This facilitates a more sustainable integration in network infrastructure, particularly in synergy with software defined networking (SDN), further promoting resource sharing/saving and interoperability [8-10]. QKD integration in deployed networks is crucial and specially challenging if coexistence of classical channels (CCs) and quantum channel (QC) is required over the same fiber. Suitable selection of parameters (e.g., channel allocation, spacing and CCs power) must be performed, considering impairments, such as channel losses, nonlinearities (NLI), and particularly spontaneous Raman scattering (SpRS). Channel allocation is relevant for optimal usage of network resources, keeping both quantum and classical transmission correctly operating [11]. Previous works demonstrated successful coexistence in DWDM and SDM scenarios [12-15], and analyzed channel spacing/allocation strategies facilitating coexistence [11, 16]. Tuneability of a commercial CV-QKD system was demonstrated, to operate in the C-band at any channel of ITU-T grid [10].

In this work, we validate for the first time the integration of open-source ETSI TeraFlowSDN

(TFS) controller [17], extended to natively support QKD technologies [18], with a real CV-QKD system enabling remote dynamic parameters configuration. This development is compliant with the ETSI GS QKD 015 specification [19], to integrate QKD technology into existing SDN environments. The reconfigurable CV-QKD system is experimentally demonstrated in coexistence with S-BVT and pluggable XFP modules in a testbed network (ADRENALINE [20]) environment, exploring different scenarios and channel allocations for both QC and S-BVT CCs to facilitate coexistence and integration within optical networks.

SDN-enabled coexistence system architecture and experimental set-up

We refer to the SDN-enabled system architecture adopting reconfigurable CV-QKD and programmable S-BVTs envisioned in [10], here reported in Fig. 1, for the sake of clarity. The software-defined QKD (SD-QKD) node consists of QKD module(s), key management system (KMS) and SD-QKD node controller [10]. The SD-QKD network controller configures the QKD nodes via south bound interface (SBI) based on ETSI GS QKD 015 [19]. The optical (classical) network includes multiple transceiver modules; SDN-enabled S-BVT are envisioned for future connectivity and multi-Tb/s scalability. To fully exploit the network resources, QC and CCs co-propagation can be performed in both DWDM/SDM domains. The SD-optical network controller coordinates both S-BVTs, through agent and SBI (e.g., OpenConfig), and the SDN optical line system (OLS) controller.

Fig. 1: SDN-enabled coexistence system architecture.

Fig. 2: Experimental set-up, including SDN-controlled CV-QKD, programmable S-BVT and 6x10G XFP modules in the ADRENALINE network (a); in the insets, CCs spectra measured at optical spectrum analyzer (OSA) in S1 (b); TFS controller service process (c) and physical layer parameters configuration in S4 (d-e); analyzed coexistence scenarios (f).

The SDN orchestrator enables joint control of QKD and classical networks, by means of ETSI GS QKD 018 interface [21].

This work focuses on SDN-controlled CV-QKD compliant with ETSI GS QKD 015 in coexistence scenarios with S-BVT. The experimental set-up is indicated in Fig. 2. The CV-QKD system consists of commercial LuxQuanta’s NOVA LQ® platform, implementing the Gaussian-modulated coherent state (GMCS) protocol with true local-oscillator laser, tunable across the C-band, and supporting up to 15 dB total loss in the QC. The signal processing routines to prepare and measure the CS, as well as to calibrate receiver (Rx) noise, are implemented real-time in FPGA, while the post-processing for QKD parameters estimation and error correction is run in a GPU-powered computer server. The SD-QKD network controller is implemented with the TFS controller integrating a dedicated QKD driver that communicates with LuxQuanta CV-QKD nodes via a REST-based SBI. It supports node discovery, application management, performance metrics and dynamic configuration of physical link parameters (wavelength, attenuation), ensuring ETSI GS QKD 015 compliance. LuxQuanta devices enable applying wavelength-change requests. A subsequent recalibration routine suspends key distillation, reconfigures lasers, estimates QC loss, calibrates Rx noise, and computes optimal state-preparation values. This process ends with a self-test to verify distillation readiness. Optionally, pre-estimating QC losses can shorten calibration; actual QC losses are always measured during routine.

The S-BVT consists of two BVT modules supporting two flows in the C-band, enabling configuration of operating wavelengths. Rate/reach adaptability is enabled by digital signal processing (DSP), with adaptive loading of the digital subcarriers [3]. The S-BVT transmitter (Tx) adopts a digital-to-analog converter (DAC) at 64 GSa/s, and external modulation (MZM) with a tunable laser source (TLS). The S-BVT Rx is based on cost-effective direct detection (DD) using a photodetector (PIN) and analog-to-digital

converter (ADC) at 100 GSa/s. The two flows are aggregated/distributed by a wavelength selective switch (WSS). Furthermore, 6 pluggable modules operating at 10 Gb/s (10G XFP from two different vendors) have been set-up in the ADRENALINE network to generate multiple signals co-propagating in the coexistence scenario at ITU-T grid channels (Cs) 28 (1554.94nm), 29 (1554.13nm), 30 (1553.33nm), 34 (1550.12nm), 35 (1549.32nm) and 36 (1548.51nm). At the Tx, the 10G CCs are multiplexed (MUX) with a 40-channel 100GHz arrayed waveguide grating (AWG) and combined with the two CCs generated at the S-BVT Tx, by using an optical coupler (OC). The aggregated CCs traverse a variable optical attenuator (VOA), to adjust the input power, and an erbium-doped fiber amplifier (EDFA). According to [15], only two notch filters are used to eliminate the amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) noise from channel corresponding to the QC. After filtering, the aggregated CCs are combined with the QC generated at CV-QKD Tx (Alice), using an optical add/drop multiplexer (OADM) with low insertion losses (IL within 0.3-0.8 dB) and transmitted over a fiber link. We consider 25 km and 50.5 km of standard single mode fiber (SSMF), as well as 25.4 km of a 19-core multicore fiber (MCF) with total losses < 10 dB, including fan-in and fan-out. After propagation over fiber, the QC and CCs are separated with a low IL OADM. The QC is received at the CV-QKD Rx (Bob), while the CCs, after an OC and a VOA (for power adjustment), are received by the XFP Rxs in the ADRENALINE network after demultiplexing (DeMUX) with a 40-channel 100GHz AWG, and at the S-BVT Rx after amplification (EDFA). A WSS is used as multi-flow distributor before DD and postprocessing, to recover the S-BVT CCs and calculate the pre-FEC bit error rate (BER). A hard decision HD-FEC threshold of $4.62 \cdot 10^{-3}$ is set.

Experimental results and conclusions

We first experimentally assess a coexistence scenario (S1) over a 25 km SSMF link, with the QC configured at channel 32 (1551.72nm), the S-BVT configured to operate at channels 31

(1552.52nm) and 33 (1550.92nm), and with 10G XFP CCs (as indicated in Fig. 2 (a)-(b) and (f)).

The performance of the CV-QKD system in terms of secret key rate (SKR, black line with round markers) and excess noise (ξ , black dashed line) is reported in Fig. 3, at the varying of the total power of the 8 CCs. The average total losses experienced by the QC are 7.8 dB. At the increase of the CCs total power, the QC performance is degraded, from a SKR of 14.12 kb/s at -1.5 dBm to 5.36 kb/s at 7.5 dBm. Beyond this power value, key generation is not possible. Within the analysed range of power, the S-BVT successfully supports a capacity of 40 Gb/s per flow at the target BER, and the 6 XFP modules correctly operate at 10Gb/s (140 Gb/s capacity).

Thanks to the programmability and adaptability of the S-BVT operating wavelengths, we reconfigure them to work at channels 27 (1555.75nm) and 37 (1547.72nm) to improve the QC-CC spacing to 200GHz, limiting the impact of NLI at high power. This second scenario (S2) allows improving the power to 9 dBm obtaining a SKR of 2.33 kb/s, as shown in Fig. 3 (in blue).

Instead of reconfiguring the S-BVT (keeping the S-BVT operating at channels 31 and 33), the CV-QKD system can be reconfigured, allocating the QC in a C-band region less affected by the NLI, due to high power and narrow QC-CC spacing. According to [13, 22] the SpRS impact is limited at channel 60 (1529.55nm) (anti-Stokes region). Therefore, the CV-QKD is reconfigured to operate at this wavelength (S3). The performance in Fig. 3 (in orange) shows that up to 8 dBm can be supported obtaining a SKR of 1.61 kb/s. In presence of more CCs the performance improvement could be even higher [13].

We also assess a CV-QKD system operating at C21 (S4, in purple). As expected, the worst performance is obtained: higher SpRS at this C-band edge (Stokes region) has a detrimental impact preventing key generation beyond 6.5 dBm.

The remote reconfiguration performed via TFS controller is shown in Fig. 2 (c)-(e). The losses experienced by the QC are 7 dB and the SKR at 6 dBm is 3.19 kb/s, as shown in Fig.2 (e).

Fig. 3: SKR (solid line) and excess noise (dashed line) at varying of CCs total power for different scenarios (Fig. 2(f)).

Tab. 1: SDN-controlled CV-QKD system performance.

λ (nm)	ξ (mSNU)	SKR (kb/s)	Loss (dB)	T_c (min)
1556.60	3.76	27.58	5.83	-
1551.72	2.56	29.34	6.07	6
1529.55	1.83	24.10	6.74	9
1551.62	3.02	26.83	6.04	7
1551.52	3.13	26.83	6.02	6
1551.32	3.01	28.79	6.02	7

The Web User Interface of SD-QKD TFS is used to configure and control QKD devices. The service creation process (Fig. 2 (c)) enables configuring the device physical parameters associated with the link. The `phys_wavelength` parameter is updated to channel 21 (1556.60 nm), confirming that the new configuration is successfully applied through the SD-QKD TFS controller and registered for the active QKD service (Fig. 2 (d)). Fig. 2 (e) shows that the wavelength update is successfully applied to the SD-QKD TFS side (`phys_wavelength` attribute).

We analyse the coexistence also over a 50.5 km link (9.46 dB measured losses). In this scenario (S5), the same channels allocation as S1 is considered. The S-BVT capacity is lowered to 30 Gb/s per CC to ensure correct transmission at the target BER. S-BVT CCs with 6x10Gb/s XFP CCs are co-propagated with the QC. The maximum power allowing key generation (at 1.74 kb/s SKR) is 0.5 dBm (in grey in Fig. 3). Similar performance (with SKR slightly higher than 2 kb/s) is obtained co-propagating the QC with the CCs (allocated as in S1) over a single core of a 25.4 km 19-core MCF, with total losses of 9 dB including fan-in/fan-out (S6, in green in Fig. 3). In all scenarios, correct operation of S-BVT and XFPs is ensured.

We finally assess the wavelength tuneability flexibly enabled by the SD-QKD TFS controller, over 25 km SSMF without coexistence. The performance, averaged over 30 minutes (min) per each case, are indicated in Tab. 1, reconfiguring continuously the wavelength via TFS controller from channel 21 to 32, 60 and considering flexible grid, with steps multiple (m) of 12.5 GHz from channel 32 (m=1, 2, 4). The measured reconfiguration time (T_c) is of 7 min in average, mainly due to the CV-QKD recalibration routine process.

We have demonstrated SDN-enabled dynamic flexible reconfiguration of a real CV-QKD system, facilitating coexistence in different scenarios with S-BVT and 10G XFP modules. The standard-compliant TFS controller design ensures interoperability, extensibility, and vendor-neutral integration, crucial for QKD deployments in heterogeneous and multi-operator environments, fostering integration in network infrastructure and faster adoption of QKD for quantum secure connectivity. In synergy with SDN-enabled networks and programmable S-BVTs, optimal resource allocation/usage can be achieved.

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